

**THE IMPACT OF DIFFERENTIATED METHODS OF TEACHING APPROACHES
AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG THE 4PS PUPIL-RECIPIENTS
IN LOREGA ELEMENTARY SCHOOL**

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The Impact of Differentiated Methods of Teaching Approaches and Academic Performance among the 4Ps Pupil-Recipients in Lorega Elementary School

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Abstract

The study investigated the level of academic performance among the 4Ps Pupil-Recipients in relation to the different methods and approaches of teaching: lecture method, collaborative learning, differentiated instruction, and teacher-student interactive method. It also assessed the Differentiated Methods of Teaching Approaches and Academic Performance among the 4Ps Pupils-Recipients in the 2nd District of the Division of Bukidnon specifically at Lorega Elementary School for S.Y. 2019-2020. The level of academic performance and the level of academic achievement of the 4ps pupils were determined. Mean and standard deviation were used as treatment of the data. The relationship between the level of academic performance of 4ps pupils and the different methods and approaches of teaching as to: lecture method, collaborative learning, differentiated instruction, and teacher-student interactive method were assessed. To determine the relationship between these variables, the data was treated with Pearson R Product Moment Correlation Coefficient at $p > 0.05$ level of significance. The descriptive correlational method of research was employed in determining the relationship between variables. Using the adopted instrument to 109 respondents, the perception of the 4ps pupils on the different methods and approaches of teaching was also assessed. Based on the data gathered, the major findings are the following: The findings showed that the “different methods and approaches of teaching” and the “academic achievement of 4P’s pupils don’t have any significant relationship. Majority of the respondents highly preferred and wanted to have a class with collaborative approach, differentiated instruction compared with lecture type method. There was no significant relationship between respondents profile in the academic achievement and there was no significant relationship between level of academic performance of 4Ps pupils-recipients in relation to the differentiated methods and approaches of teaching as to: lecture type, collaborative approach, differentiated instruction, and teacher-student interactive method.

Keywords: *teaching approaches, academic achievement*

Introduction

Learning is essential to human development, acting as the foundation for progress and a means to achieve full individual potential (Fischer & Immordino-Yang, 2008, p. xvii). Dr. Jose Rizal's famous phrase, "Children are the hope of our nation," underscores the necessity of nurturing and empowering children to achieve their utmost potential for a more promising future. Without a decent education, how can children contribute to national advancement? Although Filipinos highly value education (Philippine EFA 2015), poverty continues to be a substantial obstacle. Families struggling to meet basic needs often prioritize immediate survival over education, leading to several children leaving school to seek employment to support their families.

The Philippines acknowledges the necessity of addressing poverty-related challenges and strives to align its efforts with the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). In 2007, the government launched the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps), a conditional cash transfer (CCT) initiative modeled after the successful programs Bolsa Familia in Brazil and Oportunidades in Mexico. This initiative aims to alleviate acute poverty through investments in the health and education of children aged 0 to 18 (Montilla et al., 2015).

The 1987 Philippine Constitution requires the State to "safeguard and advance the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and implement suitable measures to ensure education is accessible to all." Based on this idea, the 4Ps program offers financial assistance to disadvantaged families contingent upon particular criteria: children must maintain an attendance rate of at least 85%, obtain required vaccines, and participate in regular health examinations. Expectant mothers must obtain pre- and post-natal care and deliver under the supervision of qualified healthcare personnel. Furthermore, parents must participate in seminars on responsible parenthood, maternal education, and effective parenting.

Beneficiaries are identified through a proxy means test that evaluates various factors, including asset ownership, type of dwelling, educational attainment of the household chief, family livelihood, and access to water and sanitation facilities. The program further reinforces the nation's commitment to achieving critical Millennium Development Goals, including the eradication of extreme poverty and hunger, the attainment of universal primary education, the promotion of gender equality, the reduction of infant mortality rates, and the improvement of maternal health. The program encompasses two primary objectives: (1) social assistance, which provides direct financial support to individuals experiencing poverty, and (2) social development, which aims to break the cycle of intergenerational poverty through strategic investments in human capital. This study evaluates the degree to which the 4Ps program has contributed to the academic success of participating pupils.

Adunola (2011) emphasizes that teachers must be familiar with a variety of instructional styles that are appropriate for the complexity of the subjects they are teaching. Pedagogical practices and strategies are critical determinants of pupil achievement. Dm and Dm

(1975) contended that pupils exhibit varied responses to different pedagogical methods, making the selection of the proper approach essential for fitting their learning styles. According to Howard Gardner's (1983) theory of multiple intelligences, pupils have different ways of learning. As a result, Ashmore, Miller, Schuckmann, and Weyler (1984) stressed that different teaching methods are needed to meet the needs of all pupils. Ladd (1993) emphasized that recognizing teaching and learning styles is the preliminary stage in improving instruction. Pedagogical strategies that encourage new ways of teaching and learning must be developed by teachers in schools that are changing (Darling-Hammond & Bransford, 2005; Saye & Brush, 2006; Swan & Hicks, 2007; Windschitl, 2002).

In *Changing Minds*, Howard Gardner posits that technological improvements can facilitate tailored learning, thereby reconciling various intelligences and learning styles (Gardner, 2006). Consequently, effective teaching tactics must cater to diverse pupil preferences and learning styles (Felder & Silverman, 1988). Nonetheless, technology by itself has not markedly altered classroom methods. Swan and Hofer (2009) noted that, although technology has been integrated into K-12 and higher education, its utilization is restricted, resulting in negligible effects on social studies instruction. Research by Windschitl (2002), Saye and Brush (2006), and Swan and Hicks (2007) demonstrates that teachers' pedagogical attitudes significantly influence the integration of technology in instruction.

Therefore, the primary purpose of this study, utilizing a survey research method, was to examine the impact of the differentiated methods and approaches employed by teachers in instructing 4Ps pupil-recipients at Lorega Elementary School on their academic performance.

Research Questions

This study investigated whether there is significant differences between the effectiveness of different teaching methods on 4Ps pupils-recipients academic performance in the public elementary school in the 2nd District of Kitaotao of the Division of Bukidnon specifically at Lorega Elementary School for S.Y. 2019-2020. Specifically this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, grade level, occupation of the parents, and family income?
2. What is the level of academic performance of the 4Ps pupils-recipients in relation to the different methods and approaches of teaching as to: lecture type, collaborative approach, differentiated instruction, and teacher-pupil interactive method?
3. Is there a significant relationship between respondents profile in the academic achievement?
4. Is there a significant relationship between level of academic performance the 4Ps pupils-recipients in relation to the differentiated methods and approaches of teaching as to: lecture type, collaborative approach, differentiated instruction, and teacher-pupil interactive method?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed an experimental research design. The independent variables included the respondents' demographic profile, which encompassed age, gender, grade level, parents' occupation, and family income, as well as the teaching methods and approaches: lecture method, collaborative approach, differentiated instruction, and teacher-pupil interactive method. The dependent variable was the pupils' test scores.

The population for the study comprised 4Ps pupil-recipients, with a sample size of 170 pupils. Of these, 48.82% (n=83) were male, and 51.18% (n=87) were female. The data for this research were derived from the academic performance assessment test scores of the pupils. The content validity of the test was ensured through moderation in alignment with the K-12 curriculum of the Department of Education. The test was developed based on the intended course learning outcomes.

Descriptive statistics and the ANOVA method were utilized for data analysis. Descriptive statistics were employed to analyze the estimated marginal means, standard deviation, and standard error of the 4Ps pupil-recipients in one public primary school in the 2nd District of Kitaotao, Division of Bukidnon, during the academic year 2019–2020.

To collect the necessary and sufficient data, an adopted survey questionnaire was used to assess the demographic profile and the academic performance levels of the 4Ps pupil-recipients. The survey also examined their performance in relation to the various teaching methods and approaches: lecture method, collaborative approach, differentiated instruction, and teacher-pupil interactive method.

Respondents

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

Grade Leve	Total Number of Pupils		Total	Total number of Respondents		Total
	Male	Female		Male	Female	
1	10	12	22	8	8	16
2	14	13	27	10	9	19
3	19	13	32	13	9	22
4	13	12	25	9	8	17
5	12	12	24	9	7	16
6	15	25	40	7	12	19

Total	83	87	170	56	53	109
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The respondents of this study were the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) beneficiaries enrolled at Lorega Elementary School during the school year 2019-2020. Out of the total 170 pupils, 109 were identified as 4Ps recipients. These pupil-recipients completed an adopted questionnaire to provide the essential data required for the successful completion of this study.

Purposive sampling was utilized in this study, as Lorega Elementary School was deliberately selected from the 2nd District of Kitaotao in the Division of Bukidnon. Additionally, all 4Ps pupil-recipients were intentionally included as respondents in the sampling process.

Instrument

The research utilized an adapted version of Elvis Munyaradzi Ganyaupfu's questionnaire, which was revised to align with the context of the study. This questionnaire was designed for the pupil-respondents and included questions about their academic performance in relation to various teaching methods and approaches: lecture type, collaborative approach, differentiated instruction, and teacher-pupil interactive method.

To assess the academic performance of the pupil-recipients, the researcher referred to Form 138 (Report Card) and School Form 5 (Report on Promotion and Level of Proficiency). These forms provided information on academic achievement, attendance, and gender. Additionally, the second-quarter grades of the 4Ps pupil-recipients in the different learning areas were used to determine their level of academic achievement.

Data Analysis

To analyze the data for this study, the following statistical tools will be utilized:

For addressing the first research question regarding the demographic profile of the 4Ps pupil-recipients, frequencies and means will be calculated.

For the second research question, which examines the level of academic performance of 4Ps pupil-recipients as perceived by the pupils in relation to various teaching methods (lecture type, collaborative approach, differentiated instruction, and teacher-pupil interactive method), the mean and standard deviation will be used.

To answer the third research question, which explores the relationship between the level of academic performance of 4Ps pupil-recipients and the different teaching methods, Pearson's r (Product Moment Correlation Coefficient) will be applied.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of data of the study. The discussion of result was focused on the impact of differentiated Methods of Teaching Approaches and Academic Performance among the 4Ps Pupils-Recipients in Lorega Elementary School.

Table 2. *The demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, grade level, occupation of the parents, and family income*

Age		
6 y.o	9	8.3
7 y.o	23	21.1
8 y.o	22	20.2
9 y.o	20	18.3
10 y.o	15	13.8
11 y.o	15	13.8
12 y.o	4	3.7
13 y.o	1	9
Total	109	100.0
Gender		
Males	56	51.4
Females	53	48.6
Total	109	100.0
Grade Level	Frequency	Percent
I	16	14.7
II	19	17.4
III	22	20.2
IV	17	15.6
V	16	14.7
VI	19	17.4
Total	109	100.0
Mother Occupation		

Farmer	26	23.9
Housekeeper	82	75.2
OFW	1	.9
Total	109	100.0
Father Occupation		
Farmer	109	100.0
Monthly Income	Frequency	Percent
10,000	109	100.0

Table 2 provides the demographic profile of the 4Ps pupil-recipients. The data reveals that the majority of respondents, accounting for 20.02%, are in Grade 3. Regarding age, most pupils are 7 years old, comprising 21.1% of the total. In terms of gender distribution, 51.4% are male, while 48.6% are female. For the mothers' occupation, 75.2% are housekeepers, 23.9% are farmers, and 9% are Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs). Notably, 100% of the respondents reported that their fathers are farmers. Furthermore, all the respondents' parents have a monthly income of less than Php 10,000.00.

Table 3. Level of effectiveness of Teaching 4P's pupils using Lecture Method approach

Statement	Mean	SD	QD
1. I want a class with visual aid, such as a slideshow, a word document, an image, or a film.	4.50	0.55	VH
2. I wanted to have a class with oral reading of a text followed by a commentary.	4.34	0.56	VH
3. Lecture method is an important part of the school curriculum at all levels.	4.45	0.52	VH
4. I prefer that the teacher has to present information and ideas.	4.44	0.50	VH
5. A good lecture can instill in a topic because of the t enthusiasm and manner of presentation.	4.43	0.60	VH
6. Lecture method can stimulate very good interest in the subject.	4.33	0.71	VH
7. I easily learned in class through lecture.	3.77	0.74	H
8. I like to have an authoritative figure at the front of a room, delivering a speech to a crowd of listeners.	3.93	0.80	H
9. Lecture can stimulate the pupil to read, think, and discuss ideas with others	3.92	0.87	H
10. I prefer a class which implies little or no class participation.	3.28	1.13	H
Overall	4.14	0.23	H

Note : n = 109 4.20-5.00 Very High, 3.40 – 4.19 High, 2.60 – 3.39 Moderately High, 1.80 – 2.59 Low, 1.00 – 1.79 Very Low

Table 3 presents the effectiveness of teaching 4Ps pupils using the lecture method. The data shows that the lowest mean score, indicating limited or no class participation, is for the statement, "I prefer which class implies little or no class participation" (mean = 3.28, SD = 1.13). In contrast, the highest mean score, indicating a preference for visual aids in class, is for the statement, "I want class visual aids, such as a slideshow, a word document, an image, or a film" (mean = 4.50, SD = 0.55). The lecture method as a whole has an average mean of 4.14 and an SD of 0.23, which is qualitatively described as high.

Alex Amartei Marmah's study identifies a significant drawback of the lecture method: it frequently renders pupils as passive recipients of information that has been pre-processed by the teacher (Hansen & Stephens, 2000). As a result, pupils often develop a reliance on the teacher for information and evade accountability for their own education (Machemer & Crawford, 2007). Furthermore, pupils who are used to inactivity may cultivate a "low tolerance for challenge" (Hansen & Stephens, 2000). Moreover, advocates of active learning contend that knowledge acquired from lectures tends to be superficial and ephemeral (Phipps, Phipps, Kask, & Higgins, 2001; Moust, Van Berkel, & Schmidt, 2005). Vedanayagam (1994) attacked the lecture as primarily a unidirectional procedure. A multitude of teachers contend that conventional lectures are inferior to active learning methodologies (Marbach-Ad, Seal, & Sokolove, 2001; Jungst, Licklider, & Wiersema, 2003).

Table 4 presents the level of effectiveness in teaching 4P's pupils using collaborative learning approach.

Table 4 highlights that the lowest-rated indicator is "working with a group allows me to focus on their learning styles," which has a mean of 4.29 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.72, but it is still categorized as very high (VH). Conversely, the highest-rated indicator is "collaborative learning," which has a mean of 4.61 and an SD of 0.49, also described as very high. The overall mean of 4.47 and SD of 0.14 further indicates a very high level of enjoyment and engagement of the 4Ps pupils in collaborative learning. This suggests that pupils greatly benefit from and enjoy learning in a collaborative environment.

Collaborative learning is founded on the principle of fostering consensus and cooperation among group members, as opposed to competition, which emphasizes individual achievement at the expense of others. In education, collaboration aims to achieve effective teaching methods that benefit the greatest number of pupils (Pugach & Johnson, 1995).

As societal challenges increasingly require collective efforts, the focus has shifted from individual accomplishments to group work and from independence to community-based collaboration (Austin, 2000; Welch, 1998; Leonard & Leonard, 2001). Gokhale (1995) explains that proponents of collaborative learning believe that actively exchanging ideas in small groups not only sustains participants' interest but also enhances critical thinking skills. Additionally, collaborative learning has been shown to develop critical thinking abilities more effectively than competitive or individualistic approaches to education (Gabbert, Johnson & Johnson, 1986; Johnson & Johnson, 1981; Johnson, Skon & Johnson, 1980).

Table 4. *Level of effectiveness in teaching 4P's pupils using the Collaborative Learning Approach*

Statement	Mean	SD	QD
1. I prefer group/team projects than working alone.	4.47	0.50	VH
2. When working with a group, it allows me to center on my learning style strengths.	4.29	0.72	VH
3. As a member of a group, I need to believe that I am linked with others in a way that ensures that the group will succeed together.	4.43	0.50	VH
4. In collaborative learning, members help and encourage each other to learn.	4.61	0.49	VH
5. When working in a group, all members are held accountable for doing their share of the work and for mastery of all of the material to be learned.	4.45	0.50	VH
6. Group collaboration is intended to promote the most effective teaching possible for the greatest number of pupils.	4.52	0.50	VH
7. In collaborative learning, pupils are encouraged and helped to develop and practice trust-building, leadership, decision-making, communication, and conflict management skills.	4.52	0.50	VH
8. Team members set group goals, periodically assess what they are doing well as a team, and identify changes they will make to function more effectively in the future.	4.42	0.50	VH
9. I like discussions, role playing, games, and other group activities.	4.40	0.49	VH
10. Active exchange of ideas within small groups not only increases interest among the participants but also promotes critical thinking.	4.58	0.50	VH
Overall	4.47	0.14	VH

Note : n = 109 4.20-5.00 Very High, 3.40 – 4.19 High, 2.60 – 3.39 Moderately High, 1.80 – 2.59 Low, 1.00 – 1.79 Very Low

Table 5 presents the level of effectiveness in teaching 4P's pupils using differentiated method approach.

Table 5 reveals that the lowest-rated indicator is the need for teachers to take individual differences among pupils seriously, with a mean score of 4.29 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.72. Conversely, the highest-rated indicator is the importance of supporting the learning process of children to help each pupil in the classroom develop their unique abilities and address their limitations, with a mean score of 4.61 and an SD of 0.49. The overall mean of 4.45 and SD of 0.12 indicates a very high level of support for differentiated teaching practices.

Table 5. *Level of effectiveness in teaching 4P's pupils using Differentiated Instruction Approach*

Statement	Mean	SD	QD
1. The purpose of differentiation is to support the learning process of children so that each individual pupil in the classroom can develop his individual capabilities and limitations.	4.47	0.50	VH
2. Teachers who differentiate instruction incorporate best practices in moving all of their pupils toward proficiency in the knowledge and skills established in state and local standards.	4.54	0.50	VH
3. Differentiated instruction can also demonstrate institutional effectiveness and equip pupils with diverse learning experiences to highly respond to increased challenges in the global society.	4.39	0.49	VH
4. More pupils grasp information and adapt it when their learning styles, modalities, intelligences, and interests are engaged.	4.41	0.49	VH
5. I am encouraged to challenge myself in task selection by choosing tasks that may not be particularly congruent with their own learning style.	4.33	0.47	VH
6. Learning through my strategy can improve writing skills and ensure success.	4.51	0.50	VH
7. It is an approach that enables teachers to plan strategically to meet the needs of every pupil.	4.47	0.50	VH
8. I believed that I have my own unique set of intellectual strengths and weaknesses.	4.42	0.50	VH
9. The purpose of differentiation is to support the learning process of children so that each individual pupil in the classroom can develop his individual capabilities and limitations.	4.61	0.49	VH
10. Teachers should take individual differences among pupils very seriously.	4.29	0.72	VH
Mean	4.45	0.12	VH

Note : n = 109 4.20-5.00 Very High, 3.40 – 4.19 High, 2.60 – 3.39 Moderately High, 1.80 – 2.59 Low, 1.00 – 1.79 Very Low

Teachers who implement differentiated instruction utilize effective strategies to guide all pupils toward achieving mastery of the knowledge and skills outlined in state and local educational standards (Anderson, 2007).

Differentiated instruction customizes education to accommodate pupils' distinct differences (Chapman & King, 2005) according to their existing abilities and comprehension, individual interests, and learning styles (Chamberlin & Powers, 2010).

From the standpoint of multiple intelligences, it is crucial for teachers to regard individual variations among pupils with utmost seriousness. Instruction and assessment should be tailored to the specific needs of each kid.

The essential point is possessing a profound interest in youngsters and understanding the distinctions in their cognitive processes to assist them in optimizing their mental capabilities. Integrating multiple intelligences with a comprehension-centered curriculum is a profoundly impactful intellectual endeavor (Brualdi, 1998; Checkley, 1997).

Table 6 presents the level of effectiveness in teaching 4P's pupils using teacher-pupil interactive method.

Table 6 indicated that the lowest-rated indicator pertains to the interaction between teachers and pupils during class, with a mean score of 4.34 and a standard deviation of 0.48. On the other hand, the highest-rated indicator reflects that interactive teaching and learning

are grounded in precise interpretation, with a mean score of 4.66 and a standard deviation of 0.48. The overall results show a mean of 4.49 and a standard deviation of 0.12, indicating that participants highly favored (rated as Very High) the teacher-pupil interactive teaching method.

Table 6. *Level of academic performance of the 4Ps pupils-recipients in relation to the different methods and approaches of teaching on Teacher-Pupil Interactive Method*

Statement	Mean	SD	QD
1. Interactive method is directed toward increasing interaction of pupils not only with the teacher, but also with each other and toward the dominance of the pupil activity in the learning process	4.59	0.49	VH
2. I want to have a position to work at my own pace and receive the satisfaction.	4.46	0.50	VH
3. Interactive learning provides unflinching support and cooperation of pupils with their teachers and other pupils in the process of acquiring new knowledge or learning new things.	4.58	0.50	VH
4. I prefer classes that require active participation in educational activity.	4.37	0.48	VH
5. The teacher's activity gives way to the activity of pupils, and the task of the teacher is to create conditions for the pupils' initiative.	4.47	0.50	VH
6. I prefer classes in which the teacher and pupils interact with each other during class.	4.34	0.48	VH
7. Interactive learning provides unflinching support and cooperation of pupils with their teachers and other pupils in the process of acquiring new knowledge or learning new things.	4.50	0.50	VH
8. With teacher-pupil interactive method, the pupils actively participate in educational activity, simulate professional situations, perform creative and research tasks.	4.52	0.50	VH
9. Interactive method is a teaching process can be a favourable atmosphere for exploring cooperative skills not only for pupils but also for teachers.	4.40	0.49	VH
10. Interactive teaching is based precisely on the interpretation.	4.66	0.48	VH
Mean	4.49	0.12	VH

Note : n = 109 4.20-5.00 Very High, 3.40 – 4.19 High, 2.60 – 3.39 Moderately High, 1.80 – 2.59 Low, 1.00 – 1.79 Very Low

According to Roders (2003), a distinctive system of social support is evident when individuals utilize their cognitive resources collaboratively to address challenges, strive towards shared objectives, and collectively furnish the requisite means to manage stress-inducing circumstances. “Interactive learning, whether conducted individually or alongside lectures, can be applied across all instructional formats (front, group, pair work, individual), albeit yielding varying educational outcomes” (Branković, 2005, 254). The findings indicate that pupils exhibit superior mastery of the subject and heightened motivation when engaged in group work compared to solitary efforts.

Reutova (2012) asserts that interactive approaches aim to enhance pupil contact not just with the teacher but also with peers, emphasizing pupil activity in the learning process.

Table 7 presents the significant relationship between the Level of effectiveness of the methods and approaches in respondent's profile in the academic achievement (n = 109).

Table 7. *Relationship between respondent's profile in the academic achievement (n = 109)*

	R	P-value	Interpretation
Grade level	.015	.876	Not Significant
Age	.026	.790	Not Significant
Gender	-.024	.806	Not Significant
Mothers Occupation	.147	.128	Not Significant

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 7 reveals that the grade-level profile has an r-value of 0.15 and a p-value of 0.876. Similarly, age shows an r-value of 0.026 and a p-value of 0.790, while gender has an r-value of 0.024 and a p-value of 0.806. These results indicate no significant relationship between these variables and the academic performance of the respondents.

Reyes and Mina (2011) found that the program led to an increase of 3 to 4.6 percentage points in the school participation rate of children aged 6 to 14. Their findings revealed that approximately 96.3% of children from 4Ps households were enrolled in school.

Table 8 showed the significant relationship between the Level of effectiveness of the methods and approaches in teaching 4Ps pupils recipients pupils and their academic performance (n = 109).

Table 8. *Relationship between level of academic performance the 4Ps pupils-recipients in relation to the differentiated methods and approaches of teaching (n = 109)*

	r-value	p	Interpretation
Lecture Method	.008	.938	Not Significant
Collaborative Learning	.033	.733	Not Significant
Differentiated Instruction	-.156	.105	Not Significant
Teacher-Pupil Interactive Method	.158	.100	Not Significant

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 8 reveals that the lecture method (r -value = 0.008, p -value = 0.938), collaborative learning (r -value = 0.033, p -value = 0.733), differentiated instruction (r -value = -0.156, p -value = 0.105), and teacher-pupil interactive method (r -value = 0.158, p -value = 0.100) show no significant relationship with academic performance. As a result, the hypothesis stating that there is a significant difference in the effectiveness of various teaching methods on the academic performance of 4Ps pupil-recipient is rejected.

Ayeni (2011) highlights that teaching is a continuous process designed to bring about desirable changes in pupils by employing appropriate instructional methods. Adunola (2011) underscores that the success of teaching depends on the suitability of methods used in relation to the subject matter. Similarly, Bharadwaj and Pal (2011) argue that teaching methods are most effective when they address the unique needs of pupils, as each pupil interprets and responds to questions differently, as observed by Chang (2010). Zeeb (2004) further emphasizes that tailoring teaching methods to align with pupils' needs and preferred learning styles has a positive impact on their academic performance.

Conclusions

In light of the findings, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Teaching methods and approaches do not determine the academic performance of 4Ps pupil-recipient based on their demographic profile.

The learning preferences of 21st-century pupils differ from traditional methods. Therefore, teaching approaches and methods should be adapted to suit the needs of this generation.

The level of academic performance of the 4Ps pupil-recipient in relation to the various teaching methods, as indicated in the null hypothesis, is rejected.

To enhance pupil performance, teaching methods and approaches need to be improved. Therefore, no significant relationship was found between the effectiveness of different teaching methods and the academic performance of 4Ps pupil-recipient.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

Teachers may reflect on their strengths and weaknesses with honesty. Revisiting the aspects of teaching that they are passionate about can help prevent frustration and foster a more enjoyable classroom environment.

Many teachers tend to forget their initial passions and motivations when faced with the responsibilities of classroom management. It is important for teachers to keep an open mind, as developing an effective teaching approach is a process of trial and error, often requiring adjustments to instructional strategies. Most importantly, teachers should adapt their teaching methods to meet the diverse needs and abilities of their pupils, acknowledging that pupils possess multiple intelligences.

Teachers may be encouraged to incorporate additional motivational techniques that align with their individual personality and teaching style. This will enable them to address various learning styles and provide differentiated instruction that meets the needs of all pupils.

Teachers should offer support and encouragement to one another, reminding their colleagues that occasional teaching setbacks do not equate to failure. The key is to acknowledge these challenges, learn from them, and continue to grow. Teachers must consistently strive to think innovatively and explore new strategies to engage their pupils. By experimenting with novel activities and ideas, teaching can become more enjoyable and rewarding for both teachers and pupils. Training sessions and workshops focused on teaching approaches suited for 21st-century pupils should be provided to improve pupils' academic performance. Additionally, teachers should adopt instructional methods that effectively enhance pupils' academic outcomes. School administrators and DepEd officials should encourage teachers to create unique teaching strategies that better align with the diverse needs of their pupils.

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